

ISic1503

I.Sicily inscription 1503

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ΡΩΣΚ

2. ΝΕΙΚ

3. ΚΟΠ

4. ΑΓ

Apparatus

Text after Ferrua 1941

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645004

Bibliography

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 269 no.42

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1503. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354243>